

Metadata in agrosystem research practice

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Abstract

This practical guide to collecting metadata in agricultural research aims to provide an easy and practice-oriented introduction to the world of data documentation. A decision tree guides researchers with simple, practical questions through the topics: 1 Why data should be documented; 2 Which forms and formats are appropriate for data documentation in your own project; 3 Which metadata should be collected for your own research data; 4 How the metadata can be created; 5 Which forms of storage and linking with the research data should be considered; and 6 How the quality of the metadata can be ensured.

In addition to the decision tree, this document also contains brief explanations of terms (Appendix I) that should be understood in order to answer the questions in the decision tree meaningfully. In addition, a metadata guide (Appendix II) with many agricultural science examples provides an overview of metadata, metadata schemas, terminologies and various forms of metadata collection and storage. Internal links in the decision tree refer to specific term explanations or further explanations in the metadata guide.

An [interactive version](#) of the decision tree was made by Justus Schneider.

The metadata guide is adapted from Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), "ARDC Metadata Guide", 1 March 2020, Zenodo. doi: [10.5281/ZENODO.6459832](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6459832), licenced under [CC BY 4.0](#)

FAIRagro

As a consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), FAIRagro is establishing a FAIR research data management system for the agrosystems research community. It develops suitable tools and workflows and thus creates the basis for sustainable plant production - now and in the future. Further information can be found on the [FAIRagro Website](#).

Helpdesk

If you need support in creating suitable data documentation or if you have any further questions on all topics relating to research data management, please contact the [FAIRagro Helpdesk](#) using the [contact form](#) or the e-mail address: dataservice@fairagro.net.

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Decision tree

Motivation for Data documentation

1. Would you like to keep your data organised and easy to understand?

- Yes** → Continue with step 2
- No** → Your data cannot be used in the long term. → Continue with the exit question

*** Exit question:** Without comprehensible data, [reuse](#) by yourself or third parties is hardly possible, and [metadata](#) is also central to the [FAIR principles](#) (findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability). Would you therefore like to create [data documentation](#), as recommended?

- Yes** → Continue with step 2
- No** → **End**

2. Is your data relevant for others (e.g. in collaboration with colleagues, project partners, [reuse](#) by third parties)?

- Yes** → Continue with step 4
- No** → Continue with step 3

3. Would you like to track and understand your data at a later date?

- Yes** → Continue with step 4
- No** → Extensive [data documentation](#) is not necessary, but at best you should still create a basic [README file](#). → **End**

Forms and Formats of Data documentation

4. Does your data contain source code?

- Yes** → Comment on the source code to achieve better traceability. → Continue with step 5
- No** → Continue with step 5

5. Do you use data with non-self-explanatory variable names or many abbreviations or codes?

- Yes** → Create a [data dictionary](#) or [codebook](#) to make your data easier to understand. → Continue with step 6
- No** → Continue with step 6

6. Do you routinely follow a standardised workflow for data collection and processing?

- Yes** → Use existing [Standard Operating Procedures](#) (SOP) or, if necessary, create a new [SOP](#) to ensure standardised workflows and reproducibility. → Continue with step 7
- No** → Continue with step 7

7. Would you like to publish your data or make it otherwise [findable](#) and [reusable](#)?

- Yes** → Collect [Metadata](#). Ideally, you should also create additional [data documentation](#) (e.g. in the form of a basic [README file](#) or as part of a [data management plan](#)) to keep your data easily understandable and thus ensure correct interpretation. → Continue with step 8
- No** → Structured recording of [metadata](#) is not mandatory for you. → Continue with the exit question

***Exit question:** Good [data documentation](#) can also be helpful for your own work within the project or at your institution. Would you like to record structured [metadata](#) for this?

- Yes** → Continue with step 8
- No** → **End**

Select [Metadata](#) to be collected

8. Is there a specific [repository](#) where you would like to publish?

- Yes** → Continue with step 9
- No** → Research suitable [repositories](#) to maximise the visibility and findability of your data when it is published. → Continue with step 9

9. Are there any specifications for the metadata schema by this repository?

- Yes** → Use this [metadata schema](#) to determine which [metadata](#) you must collect (all mandatory fields or mandatory [metadata elements](#)) and which [metadata](#) you can and want to collect (from the recommended and optional metadata elements). Ensure that you capture [all relevant metadata](#). → Continue with step 12
- No / Unsure** → Continue with step 10

10. Are there specifications for the metadata schema in your project (e.g. set out in the data management plan)?

- Yes** → Use this [metadata schema](#) to determine which [metadata](#) you must collect (all mandatory fields or mandatory [metadata elements](#)) and which [metadata](#) you can and want to collect (from the recommended and optional metadata elements). Ensure that you capture [all relevant metadata](#). → Continue with step 12
- No / Unsure** → Continue with step 11

11. Is there an established metadata schema (metadata standard) for your discipline or data type?

- Yes, one** → Use the selected [scheme](#) and [adapt it](#) if necessary to determine which [metadata](#) you must collect (all mandatory fields or mandatory [metadata elements](#)) and which [metadata](#) you can and want to collect (from the recommended and optional metadata elements). Ensure that you capture [all relevant metadata](#). → Continue with step 12
- Yes, multiple** → Check which [schema](#) best suits your data and use it to determine which [metadata](#) you must collect (all mandatory fields or mandatory [metadata elements](#)) and which [metadata](#) you can and want to collect (from the recommended and optional metadata elements). Ensure that you capture [all relevant metadata](#). If necessary, [combine several suitable schemes](#). An exchange with colleagues or competent advice (e.g. via the [FAIRagro Helpdesk](#)) can be helpful. → Continue with step 12
- No / Unsure** → An exchange with colleagues or competent advice (e.g. via the [FAIRagro Helpdesk](#)) can be helpful to [find](#) a suitable [scheme](#) or to (further) [develop it yourself](#). → Continue with step 12

12. Are there guidelines (e.g. research data policy) or specifications from your institution, funding organisation or journals regarding metadata?

- Yes** → Check whether the specifications are covered by the selected [metadata schema](#). [Adapt the schema](#) if necessary and document this. → Continue with step 13

- No** → Continue with step 13

Collecting Metadata

13. Which project phase (see [data life cycle](#)) are you in?

- Planning or data collection** → Please note that [data documentation](#) should take place directly during data collection and should be taken into account during the planning phase (e.g. in the [data management plan](#)). → Continue with step 14
- Data publication** → Use the entry form of your selected [repository](#) to save the [metadata](#). → Continue with step 22

14. Is [metadata recorded automatically](#) (e.g. file size, date, ISO value, etc. for photos)?

- Yes** → Ensure that the [relevant metadata](#) is saved and check that it is complete. If necessary, record further [relevant metadata](#). → Continue with step 15
- No** → Continue with step 15

15. Can [metadata be transferred from other systems](#) (e.g. [ELNs](#), [DMPs](#), device software, laboratory documentation)?

- Yes** → Ensure that the [relevant metadata](#) is transferred and saved, and check that it is complete. If necessary, enter further [relevant metadata](#). → Continue with step 16
- No** → Continue with step 16

16. Does (further) [metadata](#) have to be [collected manually](#)?

- Yes** → Collect all [relevant metadata](#) and, if necessary, discuss its completeness with colleagues. → Continue with step 17
- No** → Continue with step 17

Saving and linking metadata

17. Do you already use tools for metadata storage (e.g. data management tools, [ELNs](#), [digital field books](#))?

- Yes** → Continue to use these tools → Continue with step 22

No → Check whether it makes sense for you to use data management tools, [electronic lab notebooks](#) or [digital field books](#).

If Yes → Use these. → Continue with step 22

If No / Unsure → Continue with step 18

18. Is your data set extensive and complex in structure?

Yes → A clear assignment of [centrally stored metadata](#) to the respective data file can be difficult with complex data sets, which is why [decentralised storage of the metadata](#) is recommended. Should [centralised metadata storage](#) still be considered?

If Yes → Continue with step 19

If No → Continue with step 20

No → Check whether a simple [accompanying file](#) (e.g. [README file](#)) is useful to collect the [metadata](#) for your data set centrally and make it available at a glance.

If Yes → Make sure that the [metadata file](#) is clearly linked to the data record (e.g. by giving it a unique name) and that the [metadata](#) can be clearly assigned to the individual data records in order to avoid data loss. → Continue with step 21

If No → Continue with step 19

19. Are your data files frequently moved or copied?

Yes → A [central metadata file](#) is not recommended. → Continue with step 20

No → Check whether a [central metadata file](#) makes sense for the entire data set.

If Yes → Make sure that the [metadata file](#) is clearly linked to the data record (e.g. by giving it a unique name) and that the [metadata](#) can be clearly assigned to the individual data records in order to avoid data loss. → Continue with step 21

If No → check whether [decentralised metadata](#) files make sense.

If Yes → Make sure that the [metadata file](#) is clearly linked to the data record (e.g. by giving it a unique name) and that the [metadata](#) can be clearly assigned to the individual data records in order to avoid data loss. → Continue with step 21

If No → Continue with step 20

20. Is it technically possible for relevant metadata to be stored within the data files?

- Yes, completely** → Check whether you want to save your metadata directly in the data files to prevent data loss by copying or moving the data files. → Continue with step 21
- Yes, partly** → Check whether you want to store the technically possible metadata directly in the data file and supplement this with decentralised metadata files or a central metadata file. → Continue with step 21
- No** → Check whether you are creating decentralised metadata files alongside the data files in order to be able to store extensive metadata on individual data files. Make sure that these files are properly linked to the data files so that data loss is avoided when moving or copying the data. → Continue with step 21

21. Is automated searching of metadata important to you?

- Yes** → Consider machine-readable formats (e.g. XML, JSON) for storing the metadata. → Continue with step 22
- No** → You can use simple text files or tables as an alternative to machine-readable formats (e.g. XML, JSON). → Continue with step 22

Ensuring the quality of metadata

22. Have you checked the structure of the metadata?

- Yes** → Continue with step 23
- No** → Depending on the file format of your metadata file(s), you can automatically check whether they are compliant with your selected metadata schema. If necessary, use existing validation tools for this. → Continue with step 23

23. Have you checked the correctness of the metadata?

- Yes** → Continue with step 24
- No** → Check the metadata and adjust it if necessary. → Continue with step 24

24. Did you use controlled vocabularies or terminologies?

- Yes** → Continue with step 25
- No** → Use terms from controlled vocabularies to make the metadata easier to understand. Enrich the metadata with terminology concepts if necessary. This makes

them unambiguous and easier to use for automated processes. → Continue with step 25

25. Is the [metadata](#) linked to the data and documented?

- Yes** → Congratulations! You have successfully created and managed [metadata](#) for your research project. → **End**
- No** → Make sure that you link the [metadata](#) to the corresponding data and document all naming conventions, abbreviations and definitions of [metadata](#) fields used. → **End**

Appendix 1: Explanation of terms

C

Codebook / Data Dictionary

This is an important document that informs data users about the study, the data file(s), the variables, categories, etc. that make up a complete data set. It outlines the structure, content and variable definitions of a data set or data collection. The data dictionary or codebook may contain the data set layout, a list of variable names and labels, concepts, categories, cases, codes for missing values, frequency counts, notes, statements about the population, etc. This makes it an important tool for reproducibility, as it enables others to understand your data [1], [2]. The terms codebook and data dictionary are often used synonymously.

→ A [template for a detailed data dictionary](#) for field experiments is provided by [ICASA](#).

D

Data documentation

Refers to the structured and detailed description of research data, including its origin, structure, content and context. It includes information such as collection methods, collection dates, tools used and the underlying research questions. Careful documentation is crucial to ensure the verifiability, reusability and long-term archiving of data. It forms the basis for compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and contributes to quality assurance and the promotion of open science [3], [4].

Data lifecycle

The model of the research data life cycle illustrates the stages research data can go through, from the collection to its reuse. The stages of the data lifecycle can vary, but in general, the data lifecycle comprises the following phases:

- Planning research projects (including handling of the data in the research project, see [data management plan](#))
- Creation and collection
- Processing and analysis
- Sharing and publication
- Archiving
- Reuse [5]

Data management plan (DMP)

A data management plan systematically describes how [research data](#) are managed within research projects. It documents the storage, indexing, maintenance and processing of data. A data management plan is essential in order to make data interpretable and re-usable for third parties. It is therefore recommended to assign data management responsibilities before the start of a project.

The following questions can serve as an orientation:

- Which data will be generated and used within the project?
- Which data have to be archived at the end of a project?
- Who is responsible for the indexing of metadata?
- For what period of time will the data be archived?
- Who will be able to use the data after the end of the project and under which licensing conditions? [5]

Digital Fieldbooks

A digital field notebook is an electronic system or software solution for recording, managing and analysing field data. It replaces traditional handwritten field notebooks. The range of different digital solutions varies from simple digital forms for recording data in the field to comprehensive software solutions that can be used for everything from planning to data collection in the management of field experiments.

- Examples of field book apps are [Field Book](#) or [PhenoApp](#) from the Julius Kühn Institute. Comprehensive field experiment management systems include [AgroFims](#) from CGIAR or proprietary offerings such as [Agmatix](#) or [QuickTrials](#).

E

Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN)

These are digital applications that replace traditional, paper-based laboratory notebooks. They enable structured documentation of the entire research process – from planning and implementation to the evaluation of scientific experiments. ELNs offer functions such as search and filter options, facilitate collaboration through location- and time-independent access, and support compliance with good scientific practice. The requirements for ELNs vary depending on the discipline, which is why different systems exist. They are a central

component of research data management and promote transparency and traceability in research [6].

- More information on electronic lab notebooks can be found in the [ELN Guide](#) by Adam & Lindstädt (2021).
- You can find an overview of existing ELN tools in the [ELN-Finder](#).

F

FAIR-Principles

The acronym FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

Unlike other initiatives that focus on the human scientist, the FAIR principles emphasise improving the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, as well as supporting its reuse by individuals.

They are intended to serve as a guide for those who want to improve the reusability of their data sets [7].

M

Metadata

Metadata are independent data which contain structured information about other data and/or resources and their characteristics. Metadata are stored either independently of or together with the data they describe. An exact definition of metadata is difficult since the term is being used in different contexts and distinctions can vary according to perspective.

Usually there is a distinction between discipline-specific and technical/administrative metadata. Whereas the latter are definitely considered to be metadata, the former might also be viewed as research data.

In order to raise the effectiveness of metadata, a standardisation of descriptions is necessary. By using [metadata standards](#), metadata from different sources can be linked and processed together. [5]

- Further information on metadata can be found in the section [“What is metadata?”](#) in the attached Metadata Guide.

Metadata schemas and -standards

These are structured guidelines for describing research data that enable uniform and machine-readable documentation. They define which information (e.g. title, author, licence, methods) should be recorded in which format in order to ensure interoperability between different systems. The use of metadata schemas improves the findability, reusability and long-term archiving of data. A metadata schema organises the structure of metadata. It specifies which elements are mandatory for describing analogue and digital objects such as

research data, and which information should be provided in which format. A standardised data schema simplifies data entry and increases the quality of metadata. Above all, however, structured metadata enables machine readability and the exchange of information between different applications and ensures long-term reusability. Examples of established standards are [Dublin Core](#) and [METS](#). Such standards are essential for the implementation of the FAIR principles in research data management [5], [9].

The terms metadata schema and metadata standard are often used interchangeably, with a metadata standard describing a metadata schema that is widely used in the relevant community or validated by a standards organisation. [8]

- Further information on metadata schemas can be found in the section [“Elements and schemas”](#) in the attached Metadata Guide.

R

README-File

ReadMe files contain information about [research data](#), research datasets or research data collections in a compact and structured form and are often available as simple text files or in TEI-xml (.txt; .md; .xml). In this sense, ReadMe files can be published to accompany research data or can be used for structured storage of research data at the end of a project (e.g., on an institute server or [repository](#) for archiving). ReadMe files collect central [metadata](#) about the project in which the data originated (e.g., project name, persons involved, funding), provide information about naming standards used, folder structures, abbreviations, and norm data, and record changes to and versioning of research data. [5]

Repository

A repository can be viewed as a particular kind of [archive](#). In the digital age it refers to an administrated storage space for digital objects. Since repositories are generally publicly accessible or at least accessible to a specific group of users it is closely connected to the issue of [open access](#). [5]

- More information on recommended repositories for agrosystems research can be found in the [repository search](#) of the FAIRagro Search Hub or in an [overview table](#) by Rey Mazón et al. (2024).

Research data policy

A research data policy is a document that dictates how [research data](#) should be handled at a given institution.

It is supposed to contribute to the efficient management of the valuable resource research data. By now, there are research data policies for individual universities (institutional policies) as well as interdisciplinary and disciplinary policies in Germany. Even some scientific journals have their own research data policies. [5]

Reusing data

Data reuse means using data for other purposes than it was originally collected for. Reuse of data is particularly important in science, as it allows different researchers to analyse and publish findings based on the same data independently of one another. Reusability is one key component of the FAIR principles. [10]

- You can read about why metadata plays a key role in reusability in the section [“Using and reusing data”](#) in the attached Metadata Guide.

S

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

Established or prescribed methods to be followed routinely for the performance of designated operations or in designated situations. [11]

T

Terminologies (controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri and ontologies)

Controlled vocabulary is a standardised use of language in which a word or phrase has exactly one meaning. Controlled vocabulary is used, for example, when assigning keywords in metadata to describe a digital object. This keyword assignment then refers to a collection of words or phrases that are stored, for example, in a standard file for cataloguing or in an index for harvesting and retrieval. A central task of controlled vocabulary is to link synonyms that lead to the same search result [12].

In addition, there are taxonomies and thesauri that contain super- and sub-terms as well as synonyms for concepts, through to ontologies that model the properties and relationships between concepts [9].

- Further information on controlled vocabularies can be found in the section [“Content rules and controlled vocabularies”](#) in the attached Metadata Guide.

V

Validation-Tools

There are a variety of tools available online that you can use to validate metadata. The tools recommended here are intended as examples. Please check the relevant terms of use before using them:

- Examples of validation tools are the [XML-Validator](#) and the [JSON Schema-Validator](#).

Appendix 2: Metadata Guide

This Guide is intended to provide a simple generic working-level view of the needs, issues, and processes around metadata collection and creation as it relates to research data. [8]

It is based on: Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). (2020). ARDC Metadata Guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6459832>

What is metadata?

While generally ‘meta-data’ is summarised as ‘data about data’, the following provides examples of what this actually means:

- Metadata is information about an object or resource that describes characteristics of that object, such as content, quality, format, location and access rights.
- Metadata can be used to describe physical objects (e.g. soil samples, plant material and crop seeds) as well as digital objects (e.g. documents, images, data sets and software).
- Metadata can take many different forms, from free text (e.g. a README file) to standardised, structured, machine-readable, extensible content.
- Metadata is analogous to any other form of data, in terms of how it is created, managed, linked and stored.
- Metadata is associated with the data it describes. It can be embedded within the data file, or recorded a separate text/spreadsheet file that is linked to the collection of data files it describes, or contained in a catalogue record that points to the research data collection.
- Metadata enables and enhances the discovery and reuse of data. [8]

Finding data

Data formats such as text can be indexed and searched themselves (as in a simple Google search). However, the ability to search formats like audio, images and video is limited, and discoverability relies on searching the metadata. Discovery metadata helps researchers find data that, for example:

- relates to a research discipline of interest via field of research, keyword or vocabulary metadata.
- is generated by another researcher whose work is of interest via lead researcher or contributor metadata.
- relates to a geographical area of interest via geospatial metadata.
- relates to a specific crop species/variety of interest, a specific phenotypic trait of interest (e.g. root architecture, biomass growth), a specific environmental impact or

field management aspect of interest (e.g. fertilisation, crop rotation, erosion control) or a specific soil class of interest via descriptive and discipline-specific metadata.

- is generated using a specific method of interest (e.g. a specific sensor used, a specific depth of measurement, a specific software/analysis method used) via process metadata. [8]

Determining the value of data

To assess the usefulness, value and quality of a data set, researchers need to understand the context around the data. This is given in metadata that:

- describes why the data were collected, the experimental design and data collection methods
- links to the researchers and institution(s) involved
- identifies the research program or grant
- points to publications that have flowed from the research data
- explicitly provides provenance, licensing, rights, and technical information. [8]

Accessing data

Access to research data requires:

- a direct download link to online data for open access, or
- contact information metadata for the data manager for mediated access. [8]

Using and reusing data

To make use of any data set, researchers need metadata on:

- how the data is structured (e.g. table structure, time units, measurement series).
- what it describes (e.g. nutrient content, disease infestation, yield data).
- how to read it (e.g. column headings, units of measurement, coding).
- how the data was collected - including methodological details such as device types, calibrations, weather conditions, instrument settings or survey questions.
- What can be done with the data (e.g. about licence information, rights of use, public domain mark)?
- how to acknowledge the original creators by citing the data.

Proper recording of this information is important for the producers of the data as well as future users. [8]

In agricultural field trials, it is common practice to take soil samples under standardised conditions and evaluate them using specific analysis methods. If important metadata such as the exact location of the samples (GPS coordinates), the sampling date, the sampling depth,

the soil moisture at the time of sampling or the analysis methods used (e.g. potassium determination using the CAL method) are not documented, the data cannot be reliably interpreted later or compared with other data sets. Satellite or drone images also lose their informative value if metadata on the time of recording, sensor parameters or weather conditions are missing.

Levels of metadata

There are three levels of data groupings: data objects (datasets and components) can be collected into groups (collections).

1. **Collection level metadata** describes the collection as a whole. For example, the [BonaRes](#) database collects soil data from various long-term experiments (LTEs). The collection-level metadata describe, among other things, the objective, geographical coverage, participating institutes, licensing and interfaces for subsequent use (e.g. via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) or download formats).
2. **Dataset level metadata** describes individual objects. For example, within an LTE, the metadata describing the soil measurements of a specific year are on dataset level.
3. **Component level metadata** - sometimes single objects can be made up of component parts: For example, a soil dataset can consist of several layer measurements per soil profile (e.g. 0-10 cm, 10-30 cm, 30-60 cm). Each layer represents a component and requires its own metadata - such as sample depth, analysis type or storage.

The collection approach and subsequent level of description impacts on discoverability, and cost and effort of management. Metadata ideally should be based on the needs of those for whom the collection is created. [8]

EXAMPLE: Collection, dataset and component metadata

An agricultural research institute operates a central archive with data from multi-year field trials on crop rotation. To enable effective use and targeted reuse of this data, the data sets are described at several levels:

- **Collection level:** The data is organized in collections according to trial type - e.g. “Crop rotation trials under conservation tillage”, “Soil monitoring on organically farmed land” or “Long-term trials on nitrogen fertilization in winter wheat”. The collection level describes overarching metadata such as the locations of the trial sites, duration of the trial series, objectives, participating institutes and available data types (e.g. soil data, yield data, climate data).
- **Dataset level:** This level describes a specific trial year at a location, e.g. “Groß Kreuz long-term trial - year 2020”. Metadata such as tillage method, cultivated crop rotation element (e.g. spring barley), sowing date, fertilization strategy, weather pattern and harvest date are documented here.
- **Component level:** Within a trial year, the data consists of several individual measurements, e.g. per plot or measurement time. For each plot, for example, yield

data, disease infestation, nutrient analyses or drone images are recorded - each with specific metadata such as plot ID, GPS coordinates, measurement date, sensor parameters, laboratory methods used or scoring criteria.

This hierarchical structure makes it possible to find specific data - e.g. all plot yields of spring barley in 2020 under reduced tillage - without having to manually search through countless individual files. It also supports automatic linking with other data sets, such as weather or soil condition. [8]

Types of metadata

Metadata types are often grouped into functional types, but note that some elements will provide multiple functions.

The most common types are:

- **Descriptive metadata.** Information required for discovery and assessment of the collection
 - e.g. title, contributors, subject or keywords, study description, and the location and dates of the study.
- **Provenance metadata.** This relates to the origins and processing of the data, and enables interpretation and reuse of the data. It ranges from the easily human readable to the highly technical, and usually requires some knowledge of the domain to create.
 - e.g. where did the data come from? Why was it collected? Who collected it, when and where? What instruments/ technologies were used to collect the data, and how were they set up? How has the data been processed?
- **Technical metadata.** Fundamental information for a person or a computer application to read the data.
 - e.g. how is the data set up? What formats, and versions of formats, are used? How is the database configured? How does it relate to other data?
- **Rights and access metadata.** Information to enable access, and licensing or usage rules.
 - e.g. how can someone access the data? Who is allowed to view or modify the data, or the metadata, and under what conditions? Who has some kind of authority over the data? Are there costs associated with access? Under what license is the data being made available?
- **Preservation metadata.** This builds on the history from the Provenance, Rights and Technical metadata, and also includes information to allow the data to be managed for long-term accessibility.
 - e.g. has there been any restructuring or other changes to the files, e.g. due to migration to new file formats? What software has been used to access the data?

- Citation metadata. Information required for someone to cite the data e.g. Creator(s), Publication Year, Title, Publisher, Identifier. [8]

Metadata language

Understanding commonly used metadata terminology will help you better plan, collect and apply metadata. [8]

Elements and schemas

Metadata schemas are an overall structure for metadata about a particular information resource or for a specific domain. A schema specifies a set of metadata concepts or terms (called elements), and their associated definitions (semantics) and relationships. The value given to each element is the content.

Metadata schemas often emerge from a single community group (e.g. the agrosystem science community) or can be developed to describe a specific type of experiment or domain. For example, [MIAPPE](#) is a standard for describing plant phenotyping experiments and [ISO 19115](#) is an international standard for describing geographic information and services.

A schema may also specify:

- **content rules** e.g. required formats and controlled vocabularies
- the **syntax** in which elements must be encoded (or expressed), such as XML (Extensible Markup Language). [8]

EXAMPLE

One of the most common generic schemas is the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative](#), which is the most widely adopted schema for descriptive metadata to date.

It is simple and generic, with just 15 elements in the original Dublin Core Metadata Element Set, including Title, Date, Type, Format, Creator, Coverage and Rights. Dublin Core has since been extended to 55 terms in the [DCMI terms](#) namespace.

Each field can be basically free-form text, with some restrictions.

Dublin Core is used a lot on web pages, with the “dc” namespace – so you will often see things like “dc.Title” as a metadata tag inside a webpage’s HTML headers. If you are working with video, you may use Dublin Core and the MPe.g. 7 standard for video archives, and so get the “dc.Title” and the “MPe.g.7.Title” fields. Each has its own rules for how you can use them, found in the schema’s namespace (see below). [8]

Content rules and controlled vocabularies

Specifying rules around the allowable content and format of values in each metadata element improves accuracy and machine-readability of metadata, and hence discoverability of collections. Free-form text entry can lead to ambiguous data, for example, the date 3/10/15 could refer to 3 October or 10 March, in either 1915 or 2015.

Having a specific set of terms that can be used in a field, i.e. a controlled vocabulary, allows filtering and faceting of the data, improving search function.

Controlled vocabularies can be:

- locally defined (e.g. only allowing names to be selected from a list of employees), or an established standard (e.g. [AGROVOC](#) as a thesaurus for agriculture related terms, including terms for crop species or soil textures).

Likewise, formats can be:

- specified locally (i.e. names will be entered First-name Last-name), or
- use an international standard (i.e. recommended best practice for the [Dublin Core date](#) element is to use an encoding scheme, such as the [W3CDTF](#) profile of [ISO 8601](#). [8])

Namespaces

A metadata schema's 'namespace' declares a unique set of elements and definitions. By specifying the namespace(s) of the metadata schema(s) you are using, you can define which schema each element belongs to, and point people to the accepted definition of that element.

For example, the term "date" appears in many schemas. However, the way a "date" is defined or recorded may be different depending on the schema; "date" might refer variously to the date the data were published in one schema, or the date the data were collected in another schema. [8]

Finding and choosing a metadata schema

Schemas range from the very generic to extremely discipline or resource-specific:

- Generic schemas such as [DCMI Metadata Terms](#) and the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) are widely adopted and easy to use - but it is so generic that everyone can use them in quite different ways, as the description becomes more specialised.
- Discipline-specific schemas provide a richer and more targeted structure and vocabulary that allows detailed information to be provided in a more structured, granular format. Finding these can be as simple as searching the internet for "[discipline] metadata schema", from a very high level to start with (e.g. "agriculture metadata schema") and then getting steadily more specific (e.g. "crop yield metadata schema") if required. You can also search metadata schema registries such as the [Data Curation Centre's List of Metadata Standards](#) or the [Research Data Alliance's Metadata Standards Directory](#) and the [FAIRsharing Registry](#). [8]

Schemas that are often used within the agrosystem science community include the following:

- [ISO 19115](#) - international standard for geographic information

- [INSPIRE](#) - European standard for geographic information
- [Darwin Core](#) - standard for information about biological diversity
- [ABCD \(Access to Biological Collection Data\)](#) - for data about specimens and observations
- [MIAPPE](#) - Minimum Information About Plant Phenotyping Experiments
- [MCPD](#) (Multi-Crop Passport Descriptor) - plant genetics
- [BonaRes Metadata scheme](#) - for the BonaRes Repository

Adopt, adapt, or create your schema?

Although it is possible to develop a metadata schema from scratch, it is preferable to use or adapt existing standards and/or widely-established schemas, as they offer:

- Cost savings – the schema and its usage guidelines have been developed, thus saving time and effort.
- Access to help and advice – a standard is likely to have a community of users.
- Usability – users are likely to be familiar with a standard and its terminology.
- Interoperability – information can be easily shared between systems.
- Sustainability – schemas need maintenance and updating if they are to remain usable.

Your choices are:

1. If there is just one obvious metadata standard, and it meets your needs, use it.
2. If there are several obvious schemas that meet your needs, follow models of ‘good practice’ within your community.
3. Where you can find no single appropriate schema:
 - a. Adapt or extend an existing schema to better fit your needs, and document the changes you make very carefully using the documentation methods and mappings deployed by existing standards as a guide. Contact the ‘owners’ of the schema and attempt to work with them, as others may benefit from your changes.
 - b. Alternatively, develop a new ‘application profile’, where various metadata elements (and the elements’ guidelines and documentation) are taken from different metadata schemas and mixed together.

If there is absolutely no schema you can use, check again; it’s a rare situation nowadays. If there is still no schema to be found, then you may have to develop one. However, it takes a fair bit of work, and you should bring together as many interested people in your discipline as you can. [8]

Collecting and linking Metadata

Collecting metadata

Automatic metadata collection

A lot of metadata can be created automatically during the data collection process. Many scientific instruments generate metadata alongside the data itself. An obvious example is digital cameras, where some provenance metadata is written at the same time as the photo is taken, e.g. location, time and date. The same is also true for UAV images or sensor data.

Automatic metadata collection avoids data entry errors and reduces the effort required. You can also set up an automated process to sanity-check the metadata when the data comes in.

Extracted metadata collection

Some metadata can be extracted from other systems. For example, a university's human resource management, grant management or research management systems may be the best sources of information regarding researchers, research grants, or research projects.

Manual metadata collection

Some metadata requires human participation to create, and the process used depends a lot on the tools used to collect the data, for example, metadata captured in electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) or digital field books. It is also possible to build tools such as forms, which can present the metadata fields (and even pre-populate some if connected to other institutional systems) and automatically enforce the right vocabularies and data structures for each metadata record. Metadata records can be created as the data is being collected, which is preferable, or can be done later on when the researcher organises the data they have collected over some period of time, e.g. after a field trip.

Metadata is often hidden away in specification statements, database structures, data models, program code or master data reference structures. This metadata needs to be made explicit and human-readable to be useful. [8]

Linking metadata and data

There is a range of options for storing metadata, and not all metadata may end up in one place. However, searching and managing the metadata is a lot easier if you take a structured approach. [8]

Metadata within the data file

The first place that metadata can go is inside the file with the data itself. There are many digital file formats that include a range of metadata fields, and some can be extended to hold almost anything. These include:

- text formats e.g. DOCX and PDF
- tabular formats e.g. XLSX

- image formats e.g. TIFF and JPEG
- video formats e.g. MPEG
- audio formats e.g. WAV
- specialist discipline formats e.g. HDF (Remote sensing)

A benefit of storing metadata inside the file is that it moves with the file; the association between the data and its metadata is easy to maintain.

However, the downsides are:

- Not every metadata field you want may be able to be added.
- Searching the collection is slow, as the computer has to open every single file for every single query, especially as the number of files and queries grows.
- Collection-level metadata is not easily managed. If you write a collection reference into each file and then decide to make a change to it, you have to edit every single affected file. [8]

Metadata as separate files

This solution will give you infinite flexibility for storing any and all kinds of metadata without restriction: write the metadata into a separate, well-structured file, (perhaps using XML or JSON), and associate that with the data file. A common approach to strengthen the file-metadata file association is to use the same filename stem, e.g. cat1.tiff is the image and cat1.xml is the metadata. This can improve the performance for searching and metadata modifications slightly. A well-organized folder structure and naming conventions are essential here!

However, the downsides are:

- the data is still on the same storage medium, and you still have to open the same number of files to make queries or changes
- it increases the risk of separating the data and the metadata when files are moved. [8]

Spreadsheets and databases

Aggregating metadata for multiple datasets into a single spreadsheet or database gives you a lot more flexibility in searching, making changes, and in the metadata fields recorded.

Collection-level changes are very easy to make in a database, as datasets that belong to a certain collection are just flagged and pointed to the collection-level record. Only one record (the collection-level record) in the database has to be changed for every dataset in that collection to be changed.

The metadata is associated with the data by recording the filename and location (or URI) for the data within the metadata record, and updating this anytime the data location is changed. [8]

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